

BO. 11 Reshaping Plant Science: The Power of AI and Cutting-Edge Technologies

Dr. Amanulla Khan

Anjuman Islam Janjira, Degree College of Science, Murud-Janjira MS-India

Email: dramanullak@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The field of plant science is witnessing a transformative era, driven by the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) and cutting-edge technologies. AI-based approaches have emerged as powerful tools to unlock the mysteries of plant biology, revolutionizing various facets of research, from understanding plant phenotypes to unraveling the complexities of genomics and transcriptomics. This article delves into the realm of AI-driven advancements in plant scientific research, exploring how AI is reshaping our understanding of plant phenotyping, genomics, disease detection, crop yield prediction, image analysis, functional genomics, genome-wide association studies, and gene expression analysis. The integration of AI in plant research fosters innovation, sustainability, and food security, making it a transformative force in plant science research.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence (AI), Plant phenotyping, Genomics, Crop yield prediction, and Image analysis.